

DEVELOPMENT, VALIDATION, AND PILOTING OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP MODULE

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ABSTRACT

The main goal of the K to 12 curriculum emphasizes that teaching Technology and Livelihood Education plays a very important role in the attainment of the overall objective of the curriculum. The study was conducted to develop, validate and pilot test an entrepreneurship module, consisting of topics for first and second quarter, for grade nine junior high school learners. The research utilized ADDIE model which means analyze, design, develop, implement, and evaluate. A modified checklist questionnaire was used to test the level of validity of the developed module. The module was validated by technology and livelihood education head teachers, master teachers, gender and development focal persons, and the learners who have undergone the piloting of the developed entrepreneurship module. The developed module has also undergone piloting to test its effectiveness. The developed entrepreneurship module, based on the evaluation of the respondents has a very high extent of validity in terms of objectives, format, content, organization, language, gender sensitivity, and usability. The findings also indicated that the pre-test scores of learners, with a mean of 15.84, interprets as fairly satisfactory, while the post-test scores of the learners in the piloting phase of the module has a mean of 28.18 which is interpreted as satisfactory. The significance between the pre-test and post-test was then tested using Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test, it was determined that, with a p-value of $<.001$, the pre-test and post-test scores of learners is significant.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurship, Module Development, Technology and Livelihood Education, Gender Sensitivity*

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship has been viewed as an important contributor to economic growth and development (Singer et al., 2015). Entrepreneurship education programs and research have expanded significantly in the US and Europe over the past few decades (Matlay, 2008; Packham et al., 2010).

One of the top priorities of the Philippine national government is quality education. Republic Act No. 10533, also known as the "Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013" aspires for every basic education graduate to be a well-rounded individual with the foundations to excel in their chosen career. The main goal of the K to 12 curriculum emphasizes that teaching Technology and Livelihood Education plays a very important role in the attainment of the overall objective of the curriculum. Entrepreneurship is integrated in all subjects taught under Technology and Livelihood Education; it also advocates livelihood for students.

One stumbling block of implementation for K to 12 curriculum is the lack of learning module. (Cruz, 2011; Duran and Catalan, 2012). In 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic pushed the Department of Education to shift to modular instruction and other blended learning modalities to guarantee continued delivery of basic education amidst the pandemic. Learning Modules have been utilized and this gave way to the new normal in education which is blended learning. According to the Department of Education's secretary, Vice President Sara Duterte, the department eyes blended learning modality as a permanent mode of instruction. This insinuates that learning modules will continue to be utilized.

In May 2009, the Department of Education hosted a writeshop for learning materials development, thus, the last recognized module for entrepreneurship was created. The researchers noticed that some of the content of that learning module can be enhanced, and up-to-date activities will be more appropriate for today's learners. Individualized Activities to help learners in their learning process will also be taken into consideration. In 2021, Carreon, et al., stated that there is an urgent need to provide learning modules in entrepreneurship, thus they developed a contextualized entrepreneurship module for exploratory stage grade 8, this further solidifies the need for an updated module for entrepreneurship.

Research Questions

The study aimed to develop and validate an entrepreneurship module in Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) containing topics for the first and second quarter of grade nine level. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level validity of the developed module based on the of pool of experts' and learners' evaluation in terms of:
 - 1.1 objectives;
 - 1.2 format;
 - 1.3 content;
 - 1.4 organization;
 - 1.5 language:
 - 1.6 gender sensitivity; and
 - 1.7 usability?
2. Is there any significant difference between the evaluation of the learners and pool of experts on the developed module based on the criteria?
3. What are the strengths and weaknesses of the developed module in terms of the specified characteristics?
4. What are the pre-test and post-test scores of the learners?
5. Is there a significant difference between the scores of the learners in pre-test and post-test?

METHODOLOGY

Using a developmental research design, the study focused on the development, validation, and piloting of an entrepreneurship module. This approach involves a thorough and systematic inquiry with the goal of developing, improving, and assessing educational programs, materials, and processes.

The scope of this study entails the development, validation, and pilot testing of an Entrepreneurship Module tailored for Grade 9 learners enrolled at Poten and Eliseo M. Quesada Memorial National High School, specifically those undertaking the entrepreneurship subject during the academic year 2023-2024.

This study adheres strictly to the guidelines and protocols established by the Department of Education and the Schools Division of Laguna, ensuring compliance with all pertinent regulations governing educational research and development initiatives.

The respondents of the study who validated the proposed developed module in entrepreneurship were composed of purposively selected technology and livelihood education head teachers, master teachers and gender and development focal persons who have experience on instructional material writing and/or evaluating and grade nine (9) learners who undergone the pilot testing of the developed module. The pool of experts includes eighteen (18) Head Teachers, seventeen (17) Master Teachers specializing in Entrepreneurship, all possessing relevant experience and expertise in instructional materials development, alongside (7) Gender and Development (GAD) Focal persons to ensure gender mainstreaming across all instructional areas. Piloting of the developed entrepreneurship module was done in Poten & Eliseo M. Quesada Memorial National

High School. Four (4) sections with a total of one hundred and twenty-five (125) grade nine (9) learners were the respondents of the pilot-testing and they also validated the developed module.

The research used a developed module in entrepreneurship for grade 9 learners. In accordance with the Regional Memorandum of Region IV-A dated August 9, 2021, the Curriculum and Learning Management Division (CLMD) released the CLMD4A Budget of Work (BOW). This specified how the most essential learning competencies (MELC) and supporting competencies should be grouped and completed quarterly. Thus, the researchers will use the MELCs from the said CLMD4A Budget of Work (BOW).

In validating the characteristics of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module, the researchers adopted and modified a checklist questionnaire from the research of Salavaria (2014) entitled "Development and Validation of Worktext in Statistics". The researchers had sought the authorization of the owner and was given the privilege to do so. The research focused on validating the following characteristics of the developed module: objectives, format, content, organization, language, gender sensitivity and usability.

Each characteristic consists of categories to ensure the quality of the validation. Objectives is divided into three categories such as nature, purpose, and procedure. Format is divided into three categories such as structure, layout, and quality. Content is divided into three categories such as logical presentation, consistency, and quality. Organization is divided into four categories such as coherence, unity and ideas, emphasis, and relevance to discipline. Language is divided into two categories which are communicative function and language function. Gender sensitivity is divided into two categories which are gender fair language and illustrations and gender fair activities. Lastly, usability is divided into three categories such as effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction in the content of use.

The questionnaire checklist was used in the validation of the module using the given scale rating:

Scale	Range	Verbal interpretation
5	4.51 – 5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.51 – 4.50	Agree
3	2.51 – 3.50	Moderately Agree
2	1.51 – 2.50	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.50	Strongly Disagree

Lastly, as for the pre-test and post-test during the piloting of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module, the researchers crafted a fifty-item questionnaire to test the competencies achieved by the learners. The researchers crafted the questionnaire from a table of specification that is based on the budget of work given by the Department of Education.

The data from the survey questionnaire from both the pool of experts and the learners was collected, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted. Mean and percentage were used to process the data gathered from the survey questionnaire to validate the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module.

After gathering and analyzing the data from the survey questionnaire, the researchers used Kruskal Wallis test, supported by a post hoc analysis using Pairwise comparisons to test the significant difference between the evaluation of the students and teachers on the developed module based on the criteria.

In identifying the strengths and areas needing development of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module in terms of the specified characteristics, the researchers sought the opinion of the respondents who evaluated the module and complied the respondents' suggestions. A space was provided in the questionnaire for their comments and suggestions. The researchers also interviewed some of the respondents to get their feedback regarding the developed module. Lastly, the researchers took the suggestions and feedback from the pool of experts and from the learners and proceeded to revise the entrepreneurship module to achieve the desired effectiveness of the module.

A pilot-testing was then conducted in Poton & Eliseo M. Quesada Memorial National High School with four (4) sections from grade 9. A pre-test was conducted before the utilization of the developed module to gauge learner's knowledge of the lessons to be tackled. Formative tests were also utilized after every lesson of the module to assess the learners' progress. A post-test was conducted subsequently to measure the learners achieved knowledge using the developed module. The learners answered the survey questionnaire after the pilot testing of the module.

The scores of the pre-test and post-test were tabulated to analyze the effectivity of the developed module. The researchers used mean and standard deviation for the pre-test and post test scores of the learners.

Additionally, Wilcoxon signed-rank test, a non-parametrical test, was used to identify significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the learners.

The research was also limited to the development of an entrepreneurship module that covered the first and second quarter competencies of entrepreneurship for grade nine (9) learners. The pool of experts that evaluated the developed entrepreneurship module was from junior, senior and integrated high schools in the fourth congressional district of Laguna.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the level of validity of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module in terms of its lesson objectives. It reveals that the evaluation of the developed entrepreneurship module made by the pool of experts such as Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) head teachers, master teachers, and GAD focal persons focusing on the objectives, categorized as nature, purpose, and procedure unanimously received a very high extent of validity, excluding the learners who rated all the categories with a high extent of validity. This implies that the objectives of the entrepreneur module are more evident and appreciated by teachers than learners.

Nevertheless, despite the learner's rating, the objectives of the module in terms of nature still has a very high extent of validity because the objectives of the module clearly define what is to be learned, supports the realization of the general objectives of the course, attains objectives within the availability of resources, knowledge, and time, manifests a coherent structure, and expect what to know from the start of the lesson.

Similarly, the purpose of the developed entrepreneurship module obtained a very high extent of validity indicating that the module describes the intended result of the instruction, shows commitment to the goal of the subject, satisfies the curriculum requirement, requires a high level of cognition, and provides a clear goal for learning.

As to procedure, the module was also evaluated with a very high level of validity which means that the pool of experts and the learners perceived that the objectives state the possible skills to be acquired by the students upon successful completion of the subject, facilitates the students in developing study attitudes and skills, consider the goal of the learning process, addresses skills or technical procedures needed in the subject, and shows the expected amount of work to be done.

In general, it affirms that the evaluation of the pool of experts and learners across the objectives of entrepreneurship module regardless of category has a very high level of validity. This implies that there is a high level of satisfaction among all groups of evaluators, making the developed module's objectives highly valid. Additionally, the evaluations from GAD focal persons specifically demonstrate how well the module's objective aligns with gender-related factors.

McMillan (2015) and Gronlund (1998) also implied that learning objectives are critical for creating an effective instructional material. Objectives serve as guidance and a clear path that benefits teachers and students as they work toward attaining desired knowledge and skills.

Table 1. Level of validity of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module in terms of objectives.

CATEGORY	LEVEL OF VALIDITY OF OBJECTIVES									
	HT	VI	MT	VI	GAD	VI	Learners	VI	MEAN	VI
Nature	4.77	VH	4.67	VH	4.91	VH	4.50	H	4.75	VH
Purpose	4.74	VH	4.69	VH	4.86	VH	4.44	H	4.74	VH
Procedure	4.60	VH	4.58	VH	4.86	VH	4.49	H	4.63	VH
Average	4.70	VH	4.65	VH	4.88	VH	4.48	H	4.71	VH
Weighted Mean										

HT-Head Teachers, MT-Master Teachers, GAD-Gender and Development Focal Person, VI-Verbal Interpretation, VH-Very High, H-High

Table 2 shows the level of validity of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module in terms of format. It reveals that the pool of experts and the learners rated the developed module with regards to its format categorized as structure, layout, and quality a significantly favorable response giving it a very high extent of validity, apart from the learners who rated the structure with a high extent of validity. This finding supports the claim of Anselmo (2023) who stated that learners prioritize layout and structure quality.

Despite the learner’s rating for structure, the format of the module is evaluated with a very high level of validity in terms of structure because the module organized topics in a logical manner, showed attractive and readable design, and quality of print, contained adequate margins and readable type face suitable for students’ use, and demonstrates accurate and well-integrated graphics and illustrations into the text.

Correspondingly, the layout and quality of the developed module also has a remarkably high extent of validity. This insinuates that the developed module shows a visible font style and size, prevents visibility of extra marks or smudges on the paper, locates letters and graphics correctly in relationship to the lines, and exhibits a visually appealing presentation hence sustains learning. This also implicates that the pool of experts and the learners saw that the developed module illustrates carefully planned instructional designs, combines attractiveness with effectiveness on page layouts, illustrates appropriate styles and structures, consists of illustrations related for the lesson, and shows consistency of illustrations and text in the materials.

The data confirms that the evaluation of the pool of experts and learners across the format of entrepreneurship module regardless of category achieved a very high extent of validity. This insinuates that there is a very high level of satisfaction among all groups of evaluators, implying that the format of the developed module is highly valid.

Midgett, et al. (2022) emphasized that evaluation of module formats is essential for learning effectivity. Updating the format of modules can enhance learner engagement and learning outcomes.

Table 2. Level of validity of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module in terms of format.

CATERGORY	LEVEL OF VALIDITY OF FORMAT									
	HT	VI	MT	VI	GAD	VI	Learners	VI	MEAN	VI
Structure	4.60	VH	4.78	VH	4.83	VH	4.49	H	4.71	VH
Layout	4.58	VH	4.81	VH	4.74	VH	4.53	VH	4.70	VH
Quality	4.58	VH	4.76	VH	4.80	VH	4.57	VH	4.69	VH
Average Weighted Mean	4.59	VH	4.78	VH	4.79	VH	4.53	VH	4.70	VH

HT-Head Teachers, MT-Master Teachers, GAD-Gender and Development Focal Person, VI-Verbal Interpretation, VH-Very High, H-High

Table 3 shows the level of validity of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module in terms of content. It reveals that the evaluations of the developed entrepreneurship module made by the pool of experts and the learners concerning the content categorized as logical presentation, consistency, and quality has a very high extent of validity.

Remarkably, the GAD focal persons rated the developed module five (5) in most of the criteria in terms of content. This insinuates that the module delivers lessons that are accurate, organized, clear and up-to-date, covers the topics necessary in understanding the subject, includes references at the end of the lesson, maintains focus on topic/subject throughout the response, shows what is important in the topic, provides relationship of previous and present ideas, contains clear lesson introductions and summaries, and presents appropriate activities to the students.

Overall, it affirms that the evaluation of the pool of experts and learners across the content of entrepreneurship module regardless of categories such as logical presentation, consistency, and quality are very high. The validation result emphasizes that there is a very high level of satisfaction among all groups of evaluators, thus, making the content of the module highly valid.

Kizi (2022) and Shiflet, et al. (2017) implied that educational modules contain theoretical and practical content. They also argued that modules need to be adaptable, to cater diverse learning needs and goals. Integrating innovative methods on modules can provide high-quality learning experiences.

Table 3. Level of validity of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module in terms of content.

CATEGORY	LEVEL OF VALIDITY OF CONTENT									
	HT	VI	MT	VI	GAD	VI	Learners	VI	MEAN	VI
Logical Presentation	4.73	VH	4.72	VH	4.91	VH	4.55	VH	4.76	VH
Consistency	4.67	VH	4.69	VH	4.91	VH	4.53	VH	4.72	VH
Quality	4.63	VH	4.66	VH	4.77	VH	4.52	VH	4.67	VH
Average Weighted Mean	4.68	VH	4.69	VH	4.87	VH	4.53	VH	4.71	VH

HT-Head Teachers, MT-Master Teachers, GAD-Gender and Development Focal Person, VI-Verbal Interpretation, VH-Very High, H-High

Table 4 shows the level of validity of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module in terms of content. It reveals that the evaluations from the pool of experts and the learners for the developed entrepreneurship module made by regarding organization categorized as coherence, unity and ideas, emphasis, and relevance to discipline received a very high extent of validity. However, learners rated unity and ideas and emphasis slightly lower but still has a high extent of validity, same goes for GAD focal persons who rated relevance to discipline with a high extent of validity.

Nonetheless, the developed module reached a very high extent of validity in terms of coherence, this implies that the developed module displays a main idea that is supported by details that fit where they are placed, includes sequencing that makes sense and helps the reader understand what is written, uses a logical structure, shows natural and appropriate paragraphing, and contains a clear sense of order.

Considering unity and ideas of the organization, even with the evaluation of learners which obtained a high extent of validity, the developed module reached an overall very high validity in terms of unity and ideas. This insinuates that the developed module consists of order which makes sense and easy to follow, connects ideas with smooth transitions, guides the reader through the chain of reasoning or progression of ideas, responds to the prompt, and displays logical flow of ideas.

As for the emphasis of the organization, despite having high level of validity from the learners, the overall evaluation from all respondents reached a very high extent of validity. This means that the developed module provides necessary supporting details and illustrations, shows single, distinct focus, presents well-developed ideas or narrative, expresses sense of completeness, uses real-life examples.

With regards to relevance to discipline, despite the rating of GAD focal persons of high level of validity, the developed module still falls into the scope of very high extent of validity. This suggests that the module contains an inviting lead that grabs the reader's attention, embraces a strong conclusion that brings an ending to what is written, catches the audience 's attention effectively but still is connected to the area of discipline, makes connections between disciplines, and uses a unique and effective organizational structure for the purpose and audience.

Summing up, the data supports that the evaluation of the pool of experts and learners across the organization of the entrepreneurship module regardless of categories received a very high level of validity. This implies that the organization of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module is highly valid.

Savenko and Shniukova (2023) noted that module organization involves dividing the content into independent topics to improve the flexibility and individualized learning of learners. Improvements on the organization in terms of presenting the ideas in the developed module should be done to achieve better outcomes.

Table 4. Level of validity of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module in terms of organization.

CATEGORY	LEVEL OF VALIDITY OF ORGANIZATION									
	HT	VI	MT	VI	GAD	VI	Learners	VI	MEAN	VI
Coherence	4.64	VH	4.72	VH	4.80	VH	4.56	VH	4.70	VH
Unity and Ideas	4.72	VH	4.66	VH	4.74	VH	4.46	H	4.70	VH
Emphasis	4.63	VH	4.62	VH	4.80	VH	4.48	H	4.66	VH
Relevance to Discipline	4.52	VH	4.67	VH	4.46	H	4.52	VH	4.57	VH
Average Weighted Mean	4.63	VH	4.67	VH	4.70	VH	4.51	VH	4.66	VH

HT-Head Teachers, MT-Master Teachers, GAD-Gender and Development Focal Person, VI-Verbal Interpretation, VH-Very High, H-High

Table 5 shows the level of validity of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module in terms of language used. It reveals that from the evaluation done by the pool of experts and the learners that the developed entrepreneurship module concerning language categorized as communicative function and language function got a significantly favorable response across all criteria achieving a very high extent of validity. Additionally, the evaluations from GAD focal persons specifically demonstrate how well the module's language aligns with gender-related factors.

In terms of communicative function, the developed module utilizes words that are free from grammatical errors, provides instructions/directions that are clear and easy to follow, develops a language structure that avoids misinterpretation, presents the topics and subtopics clearly, and fits audience and purposes in terms of its sentence style.

As to language function, it can be seen that the developed module uses English language as the medium of instruction, makes use of a language that is simple and easy to understand, chooses words for their precise meaning and uses an appropriate level of specificity, demonstrates superior knowledge of the language and basic concepts and operations and applies various sentences, yet clearly structured and carefully focused.

With this in mind, the data implies that the language used in the developed module is highly valid. The use of language is important when developing a module. It is one of the factors to have an effective tool that is modified for learners' needs and capabilities (Marita, et al. (2022); Nardo (2017); and Pléh (2022)).

Table 5. Level of validity of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module in terms of language.

CATEGORY	LEVEL OF VALIDITY OF LANGUAGE									
	HT	VI	MT	VI	GAD	VI	Learners	VI	MEAN	VI
Communicative Function	4.66	VH	4.72	VH	4.80	VH	4.57	VH	4.70	VH
Language Function	4.68	VH	4.86	VH	4.89	VH	4.61	VH	4.79	VH
Average Weighted Mean	4.67	VH	4.79	VH	4.84	VH	4.59	VH	4.75	VH

HT-Head Teachers, MT-Master Teachers, GAD-Gender and Development Focal Person, VI-Verbal Interpretation, VH-Very High, H-High

Table 6 shows the level of validity of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module in terms of gender sensitivity. The data reveals that gender sensitivity categorized as gender fair language and illustrations and gender fair activities got a significantly favorable response from the pool of experts and learners. The evaluation emphasizes that there is a high level of satisfaction among all groups of evaluators. Additionally, the evaluations from GAD focal persons specifically demonstrate how well the module's gender sensitivity aligns with gender-related factors.

With regards to gender fair language and illustrations, it is ensured that the developed module utilizes words that are gender neutral or free from gender bias, provides definitions and examples that are free from stereotypes, uses illustrations that show equal opportunities for all genders, uses examples that shows the capabilities of all learners, and uses words that uplift all gender and their capabilities.

As for gender fair activities, the developed module provides learning activities that give equal opportunity for all learners to show their skills and capabilities, gives criteria that are fair and contains no discrimination against any gender, utilizes resources for activities that are abundant and accessible to all types of learners, provides equal opportunities to varied types of learners to excel in the provided activities, and gives learning activities that are free from gender stereotypes.

The data implies that in terms of gender sensitivity, the developed module is highly valid. Suhrcke and Thomaschewski (2018); Yuden, et al. (2020); and Domogen et al. (2022) confirmed that gender sensitivity is vital in promoting gender equality and gender biases inside the classroom. Butler (2023) further emphasized that gender inclusive modules positively influence learners' attitudes and learning outcomes. Within this context, the researchers ensured that the developed Entrepreneurship module is gender fair and contains no biases against any gender.

Table 6. Level of validity of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module in terms of gender sensitivity.

CATEGORY	LEVEL OF VALIDITY OF GENDER SENSITIVITY									
	HT	VI	MT	VI	GAD	VI	Learners	VI	MEAN	VI
Gender Fair Language and Illustrations	4.66	VH	4.69	VH	4.83	VH	4.58	VH	4.70	VH
Gender Fair Activities	4.73	VH	4.73	VH	4.74	VH	4.63	VH	4.73	VH
Average Weighted Mean	4.69	VH	4.71	VH	4.79	VH	4.61	VH	4.72	VH

HT-Head Teachers, MT-Master Teachers, GAD-Gender and Development Focal Person, VI-Verbal Interpretation, VH-Very High, H-High

Table 7 shows the level of validity of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module in terms of usability. It reveals that the evaluations of the developed entrepreneurship module made by the pool of experts and the learners regarding usability categorized as effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction in the content of use got a significantly favorable response and it emphasizes that there is a high level of satisfaction among all groups of evaluators.

For usability in terms of effectiveness, the developed module shows usefulness in understanding the different concepts of the subject, helps in responding to the students' need of understanding the subject, serves as a useful and effective instructional material, adapts to students' interests and abilities, and communicates knowledge and ideas effectively.

With regards to usability in terms of efficiency, the developed module uses a design that supports ease of learning, strengthens the learning interests of the students, encourages the student to work at their own pace, reinforces the transfer of learning, and encourages students in completing the given task.

As for satisfaction in the content of use, the developed module exhibited attributes such as offering meaningful experiences to the learners in learning the lessons, provides useful information, graphics, and illustrations to better understand the topics presented, develops new knowledge and skills, stimulates enthusiasm for further learning, and presents intellectually stimulating learning activities.

The data implies that the developed module is highly valid in terms of usability. Deraniyagala, et al. (2015); Aziz and Mamat (2019); Connan, et al. (2019); Alshare, et al. (2022) and Murphrey (2023) agreed that usability of modules is a key factor to consider in assessing the effectiveness of a material for learning experiences. Learnability, readability, practicality, and difficulty of activities in the material is some of the factors to consider when evaluating usability of a leaning material, all of which impacts the overall user experience and retention of knowledge for learners.

Table 7. Level of validity of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module in terms of usability.

CATEGORY	LEVEL OF VALIDITY OF USABILITY									
	HT	VI	MT	VI	GAD	VI	Learners	VI	MEAN	VI
Effectiveness	4.66	VH	4.71	VH	4.86	VH	4.55	VH	4.71	VH
Efficiency	4.52	VH	4.74	VH	4.77	VH	4.59	VH	4.65	VH
Satisfaction in the Content of Use	4.60	VH	4.79	VH	4.91	VH	4.63	VH	4.73	VH
Average Weighted Mean	4.59	VH	4.75	VH	4.85	VH	4.59	VH	4.70	VH

HT-Head Teachers, MT-Master Teachers, GAD-Gender and Development Focal Person, VI-Verbal Interpretation, VH-Very High, H-High

Table 8 shows the difference between the evaluation of the learners and pool of experts based on the identified characteristics. It can be observed on the data that there is a significant difference between the evaluation of respondents in terms of objectives, format, content, organization, language, and usability. Whereas there is no significant difference in terms of gender sensitivity.

Based on the post hoc analysis conducted, there is a significant difference between the learners' evaluation compared to pool of experts' evaluation in terms of objectives. It can also be seen that head teachers, master teachers and GAD focal persons appraised the module with a very high level of validity of objectives while learners have given the developed module with a high extent of validity.

This implies that the pool of experts appreciated the objectives of the developed module more than the learners. The following findings agrees with Anselmo (2023) who stated that teachers value the module's learning objectives more than learners because the teacher's experience influences their appreciation of learning objectives compared to learners.

In terms of format, there is a significant difference found between the evaluation of the learners against the evaluation of master teachers and gender and development focal persons. This implies that master teachers and GAD focal persons appreciated the format of the developed module more than the learners.

This mean that learners are more critical in evaluating a modules format because they consider the layout and graphics included in the material. This aligns with the findings of Anselmo (2023) who concluded that teachers and learners exhibit different perspectives when evaluating a module format. He further emphasized that learners desire higher quality in terms of layout and structure compared to teachers. His findings solidify the claim of Pallegama (2020) that learners prefer modules with more visually appealing and organized materials.

In terms of content, there is a significant difference found between the evaluation of the learners against the evaluation of master teachers and gender and development focal persons. Based on the data, master teachers and gender and development focal persons appreciated the developed module more than the learners.

This significant difference between the evaluation of teachers and learners may root from the difference of their view on the content of the module. Warren and Bartholomew (2016) defended this claim when he stated that the difference in evaluations from teachers and learners stem from different perspectives and priorities in the learning process. Teachers prioritize the alignment of content with learning outcomes.

In terms of organization, a significant difference is found between the evaluation of learners and master teachers. Based on the data, master teachers appreciated the organization of the module more in contrast with the evaluation of the learners.

This significance between the evaluation of master teachers and learners was justified by De Guzman (2022) who stated that teachers and learners differ in evaluating module organization. Teachers focus on the strengths and weaknesses of the teaching and learning processes, while learners emphasize material resources, assessment methods.

In terms of language, there is a significant difference between the evaluation of learners and master teachers. Based on the data, the master teachers gave the developed module a significantly higher rating in compared to the rating of learners.

The significant difference in their evaluations was due to different perspective that they consider in rating the developed module. According to Rath (2022) teachers' focus on evaluating the language used in a module focuses on assessing learners' language skills. On the other hand, Yuzar (2022) claimed that learners' evaluation of language in a module focuses on addressing their needs and their problems in language skills.

In terms of usability, there is a significant difference found between the evaluation of the learners against the evaluation of master teachers and gender and development focal persons. Based on the data on their evaluation, the teachers appreciated the usability of the developed module more than the learners.

Holland (2018) claimed that learners focus more on the usability and suitability of the modules to improve their learning experience. Teacher and learner evaluations of usability in modules differ in focus and outcomes. Furthermore, according to Phongphaew et al. (2017), teacher evaluations aim to improve the effective usage of learning resources by assessing standard modules. On the other hand, according to Phongphaew and Jiamsanguanwong (2017), learner evaluations emphasize the ease of use of the module to enhance user satisfaction. While teachers' evaluations focus on enhancing tools and approaches for effective teaching, learners' evaluations prioritize enhancing the learning experience through improved design and usability.

Despite having a significant difference in the characteristics mentioned above, learners' evaluation on the developed module was still highly valid, thus, supporting the validity of the entrepreneurship module.

Lastly, as for the gender sensitivity of the developed module, after conducting the post hoc analysis, it shows that there is no significant difference between the evaluation of the learners and teachers, this implies the gender-neutral representation of the developed module.

Thaçi and Sopi (2022), Almutairi and Sharaid (2021), Borch, et al. (2020) and Botaccio, et al. conformed that the evaluation of teachers and learners can differ based on the assessment method used and perspectives and subjectivism.

According to Holland (2018); Wei (2020); and Anselmo (2023), learners' evaluation leans more towards the layout, structure and the knowledge they will gain in the learning material, while teachers appreciate objectives and recognizes teaching strategies. Considering this, it is important to give importance to both evaluations by teachers and learners. They also stated that involving learners in module evaluation can enhance their learning experience and contribute to module improvement.

Table 8. Difference between the evaluation of the learners and teachers based on the characteristics.

CHARACTERISTICS	COMPUTED VALUE	P-VALUE	INTERPRETATION
Objectives	18.711	<.001	Significant
Format	12.874	0.005	Significant
Content	13.357	0.004	Significant
Organization	8.204	0.042	Significant
Language	8.185	0.042	Significant
Gender Sensitivity	2.822	0.420	Not Significant
Usability	8.056	0.045	Significant

Table 9 shows the feedback from the respondents, focusing on the strengths of the developed module in entrepreneurship. The objectives were commended the respondents stating that the goals are clearly stated and attainable. The format was also lauded, noting that the visuals, illustrations, graphics, and layout of the developed module makes it easy for learners to understand the lesson being discussed. As for the content of the developed module, all respondents commended the attention to detail and clarity of the entrepreneurship module. They also noted that the activities are effective and cater to the needs of diverse learners. The respondents also emphasized that the organization of the module was impeccable, stating that the developed module is clear and systematic. With regards to language, it was also appreciated by the respondents, stating that the developed module used correct grammar. Lastly, the usability of the developed entrepreneurship module was commended by the pool of experts and the learners.

Given the following feedback, it can be insinuated that the developed module will equally benefit teachers and learners. Furthermore, the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module can aid the deficiency of resources in teaching entrepreneurship for grade nine.

Murphrey, et al. (2023), Pruszko, et al. (2023), Hidayat and Utomo (2021) Lazar, et al. (2021) and Fajardo-Flores, et al. (2017) highlighted the importance of evaluating content and usability. Considering the feedback of evaluators in enhancing module design and functionality is also essential in module development.

Table 9. Strengths of the developed entrepreneurship module based on the feedback of the respondents.

Category	Feedback
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The goals are clearly stated and attainable.
Format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The graphics, illustrations, and layout are well structured making it easy for learners to follow and understand complex concepts.
Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The topics are thorough and have well-organized information. The module is clear and easy to understand. The exercises and assessments effectively reinforce key points. Promoting active engagement for diverse learners.
Organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clear and systematic learning material.
Language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The module used correct grammar.
Usability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The module exhibits competence in meeting the needs that can help the learners grow.

Table 10 shows the areas needing improvement on the developed entrepreneurship module based on the feedback of the respondents. The respondents established that there is a need to improve the technical format of the developed module, especially the font size of the examples given. They also emphasized the need to revise the developed module's format to fit the learning resource standards of the Department of Education to be accepted as an approved learning material. Suggestions regarding the content were made. Using a self-learning questionnaire to assess one's personal entrepreneurial competencies and making more lessons considering the most essential learning competencies. Lastly, for usability, the respondents suggested considering learners' safety in some of the performance tasks and that activities should be closely monitored. This deduction about the module's usability may be connected to some performance tasks which ask learners to have an interview in the community. With these development areas in mind, it can be insinuated that continuous updating and evaluation of the developed module be done.

Goncu-Berk (2022) agrees with the suggestions to improve the technical formatting of the developed module. He implied that font size used in instructional modules is an important factor in achieving readability and usability of a developed instructional material.

Table 10. Areas needing improvement on the developed entrepreneurship module based on the feedback of the respondents.

Category	Feedback
Format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make it appropriate for Learning Resource standard, please follow the format and guidelines used in crafting learning materials. • Use readable font.
Content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use self-learning questionnaire to assess one's PECs. • Please create more lessons related to MELC.
Usability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include the safety of learners to some performing tasks. Activities should be facilitated well and closely monitored. • Add guided questions that served as a motivation for higher order thinking skills.

Table 11 shows the pre-test and post-test scores of the learners. Four sections tallying to one hundred twenty-five (125) learners participated in the pilot testing of the developed module. The pre-test scores of the learners have a mean of 15.84 which interprets as fairly satisfactory. The lowest score from the pre-test was seven (7) while the highest score was forty (40) out of fifty (50) items.

Berry (2008) and Hornbuckle (2022) stated that pre-tests are intended to evaluate learners' prior knowledge and give teachers opportunity to identify learning gaps. Janelli and Lipnevich (2021) and Broedell, further emphasized that pre-tests are a useful tool that can aid teachers to tailor their lessons to meet the needs of the learners. Additionally, the result of the pre-test was used to track learner progress during the course.

Table 12 shows the post-test scores of the learners. Scores from the post-test of the learners have a mean of 28.18 which interprets as satisfactory. The lowest score from the pre-test was eight (8) while the highest score was fifty (50) out of fifty (50) items.

The standard deviation of the pre-test insinuates that there is a wide difference comparing the learners' scores. The standard deviation for the post-test rosed, implying that the score of the learners varied differently more in the post-test than the pre-test.

Dombrowski and Gischlar (2015), Park (2015) and Hornbuckle (2022) emphasized that post-test is critical for evaluating the effectiveness of interventions and tracking progress and improvement of learner's performance.

Table 11. Pre-test and post-test scores of the learners.

	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Scores in Pre-Test	15.84	6.64	Fairly Satisfactory
Scores in Post-Test	28.18	9.95	Satisfactory

Table 12 shows the difference on the percentage scores of learners based on the competencies discussed in the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module. Based on the data presented, the learners had the highest improvement on the topic selecting a business. On the other hand, the learners got the lowest improvement based on their scores on forms of business organization and steps in making the business legal. It can also be observed that learners' score increased in all lessons tackled by the developed module.

It can be insinuated that the developed module has helped the learners improve their knowledge in entrepreneurship in all the topics discussed. However, additional intervention must be considered to further improve the scores of the learners.

According to Garingan (2023), modules play a important role in facilitating learning among learners by promoting self-paced learning, enhancing study skills, and improving learning outcomes. The use of modules in education has been shown to positively impact learners' performance. However, Lumanta et al. (2022) stated that to ensure the effectiveness of the modular approach, continuous evaluation, updating of tasks, modern strategies, and the integration of technology applications in teaching are recommended.

Table 12. Difference on the percentage scores of learners based on the competencies discussed in the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module.

TOPIC	PRE-TEST	POST-TEST	DIFFERENCE
Concepts of entrepreneurship	37%	60%	23%
Personal entrepreneurial competencies (PEC) clusters	33%	62%	29%
Types of business plan	29%	57%	28%
Steps in making a business plan	28%	56%	28%
Analyzing business opportunities in the community	29%	47%	18%
Selecting a business	34%	67%	33%
Forms of business organization	27%	44%	17%
Designing a business organization	38%	73%	35%
Steps in making the business legal	33%	51%	17%

Figure 3 shows the scores of the learners in formative assessments during the pilot testing of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module. The data reveals that the average of learners' score got the highest of 4.8 in the lesson of designing a business organization while their average scores got the lowest score of 2.5 in the topic forms of business organization. This is because some terms in the forms of organization are vague and can be easily confused with each other. However, the researchers made it a point to reinforce and gave intervention so that learners will further understand the lesson.

According to Alemann (2022) formative assessment occurs immediately following instruction to gauge student understanding and guide future teaching. On the other hand, Magdalena and Kumarani. (2023) defined summative assessment as an evaluation conducted at the end of a learning period to determine overall student achievement and progression. It can also be insinuated through the data that the average scores of the learners in the formative assessments are slightly higher than the post test.

Figure 3. Scores of the learners in formative assessments during the piloting of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module.

Table 13 shows the difference between the scores of the learners in pre-test and post-test. Pre-test and post-test scores were tested for normality, considering the result of the normality test, the pre-test was found not normally distributed thus, the researchers used nonparametric treatment for the data. The table shows that there is a significant difference between the pre-test and the post-test of the learners this implies that the developed module was effective in aiding the learning process of the learners. Objective setting at the beginning of the lesson, consistent format, organization, language used,

along with the comprehensive content of the module and inclusive activities helped learners to have an improved understanding of the topics. The developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module has helped learners understand the concepts better.

Torre Franca (2017), Carreon, et al. (2020) and Lumapenet (2023) justified that developing a module is an effective tool for achieving improved learning outcomes. Furthermore, Shaifuddin, et al. (2022) and Edo, et al. (2022) insinuated that developing a module is important in enhancing learning outcomes and promoting independent learning. Creating organized instructional material aids in delivering content efficiently.

Table 13. Difference between the scores of the learners in pre-test and post-test

Variables	Computed Value	p-value	Interpretation
Scores of Pre and Post Assessments	9.297	<.001	Significant

Conclusions

The developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module was validated according to the following characteristics: objectives, format, content, organization, language, gender sensitivity and usability. The study has found that the developed module achieved a very high extent of validity in terms of all the specified characteristics, implying that the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life is highly valid in all characteristics.

Significant difference between the evaluation of the learners and pool of experts on the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module was found in objectives, format, content, organization, language, and usability. These findings were supported by different studies that denotes that the difference between the evaluation of learners and teachers is caused by different views, priorities, and experiences. Contrastingly, in terms of gender development, there was no significant difference found between the evaluation of the respondents, implying the gender-neutral representation of the developed module.

The developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module was lauded for clearly stating goals that are attainable and for having graphics, illustrations, and layout that are well structured. The respondents also commended the developed module for having well organized topics that are clear and easy to understand along with exercises and assessments that promote active engagement for diverse learners. Correctness of grammar and the developed module's usability was also complimented by the respondents. Finally, the effectiveness and efficiency of the developed module was evident resulting to the satisfaction of the evaluators in the ease of use of the entrepreneurship module.

As for the areas needing development in the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module, the respondents suggested to use a more readable font and to align it with the learning resource standards of the Department of Education for it to be acknowledged by the department. It was also emphasized that safety of learners must be considered in some of the activities and to closely monitor the learning tasks. Lastly, adding more guided questions were suggested to encourage higher order thinking skills of learners.

Four sections tallying to one hundred twenty-five (125) learners participated in the pilot testing of the developed module. The pre-test scores of the learners have a mean of 15.84 which interprets as fairly satisfactory. The lowest score from the pre-test was seven (7) while the highest score was forty (40) out of fifty (50) items. On the other hand, scores from the post-test of the learners have a mean of 28.18 which interprets as satisfactory. The lowest score from the pre-test was eight (8) while the highest score was fifty (50) out of fifty (50) items. It was found that the standard deviation of the post-test is higher than that of the pre-test, implying the wider range of scores in post-test than in pre-test.

The findings also showed that there was a significant difference between the pre-test and the post-test scores of the learners, this was supported by the scores of the learners during the piloting of the developed module. This implies that the developed module was effective in aiding the learning process of the learners.

Recommendations

After verifying the findings and conclusions revealed from this study, the researcher came up with the following recommendations:

1. Revision of the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module according to the Department of Education's learning resource format and have it recognized by the department.
2. Revision and additional activities for topics with lower learning improvements to further reinforce learning.
3. Conduct further testing with regards to the effectivity and usability of the developed module in a larger scale.
4. Use the developed entrepreneurship in everyday life module as a supplementary instructional material in teaching entrepreneurship.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers have undergone the following procedures in data gathering:

The researchers conducted a survey using a modified questionnaire, validated by the panel, to measure the validity of the module. To conduct the study, the researchers

seek the endorsement of the Schools Division Superintendent, Schools District Supervisor, and the principals of junior high schools and integrated high schools in the fourth district of Laguna.

Afterwards, the researchers were endorsed to head teachers, master teachers and GAD focal person of the schools. The researchers introduced themselves and the purpose of the study. The researchers then distributed the questionnaires and developed entrepreneurship module and explained the evaluation process. The modified questionnaire consists of a likert scale that is divided into the set of characteristics such as objectives, format, content, organization, language, gender sensitivity, and usability to evaluate the module was used. The researchers have given the pool of experts' adequate time to evaluate the developed entrepreneurship module.

The pilot-testing was then conducted in Poton & Eliseo M. Quesada Memorial National High School with four (4) sections from grade 9, tallying with a total of 125 learners.

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Memorandums

- Deped CALABARZON Regional Memo No. 383 S. 2021
 - DepEd Order No. 32, series of 2017 entitled "Gender-Responsive Basic Education Policy"
 - Republic Act No. 10533, "Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013"
-